

HYGROTHERMALLY STABLE LAMINATES WITH EXTENSION-TWIST AND BEND-TWIST COUPLINGS

R. Haynes*, E. Armanios

Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Texas at Arlington, Arlington, TX, USA

* Corresponding author (rahaynes@uta.edu)

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1 Summary

The material-independent hygrothermal-stability conditions are derived from Classical Lamination Theory (CLT) [1] and used in conjunction with specific compliance coefficients in an optimization routine to identify hygrothermally stable stacking sequences with optimal coupling [2]. Of particular interest is the combined effect of extension-twist and bend-twist couplings. The objective is to achieve the highest twist distribution possible among flat laminates of a given number of plies. Optimal stacking sequences are presented for flat laminates with up to ten plies.

2 Introduction

Laminated composite materials have the potential for coupling of deformation modes in ways not achievable with conventional materials. For example, a rotor blade constructed with a laminate exhibiting extension-twist coupling can passively change its twist distribution with increasing rotor speed, and thereby change its angle of attack. This effect has been shown to achieve maximum efficiency in tilt rotor aircraft in both the vertical and forward flight regimes, with measurable horsepower savings [3].

Lifting surfaces are also subject to transverse aerodynamic lift forces, which often induce bending moments in the structure. A lifting surface made from a laminate with bend-twist coupling can passively change its twist distribution upon experiencing a change in lift. This has application in aircraft with swept-forward wings; in this case an increase in lift can produce a change in twist distribution that reduces the angle of attack, which in turn can delay the onset of aerodynamic instabilities such as divergence. Further increase in efficiency in

tilt rotor as well as variable speed rotor aircraft could be achieved by designing blades with both extension-twist and bend-twist couplings

Some couplings, such as extension-twist coupling, require the use of asymmetric stacking sequences, which are prone to hygrothermal instabilities. Hygrothermally unstable laminates will warp out-of-plane with changes in temperature or moisture. Since this behavior is typically undesirable, this work aims at identifying only hygrothermally stable laminates with the couplings mentioned previously. Families of hygrothermally stable asymmetric stacking sequences have been published previously by Winckler [4] but have not been shown to be unique or optimal. This work makes use of the necessary and sufficient conditions for hygrothermal stability, derived previously [5] to ensure the entire domain of hygrothermally stable laminates are considered.

A laminate with both extension-twist and bend-twist couplings has the potential for greater twist distribution changes than either coupling alone. The present work analyzes all families of hygrothermally stable laminates for optimal combined extension-bend-twist couplings. Next, a constrained optimization is performed to identify stacking sequences that produce the highest twist rate achievable from coupling of deformation modes.

3 Hygrothermal Stability Conditions

The necessary and sufficient conditions for hygrothermal stability have been derived in previous work [5]. A summary will be provided in the following for convenience. The relationship between force and moment resultants and the mid-plane strains and curvatures are expressed in CLT as

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_{xx} \\ \kappa_{yy} \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} N_{xx}^{(T,H)} \\ N_{yy}^{(T,H)} \\ N_{xy}^{(T,H)} \\ M_{xx}^{(T,H)} \\ M_{yy}^{(T,H)} \\ M_{xy}^{(T,H)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where N_{xx} , N_{yy} , N_{xy} , ε_{xx} , ε_{yy} , γ_{xy} are the in-plane forces and strains respectively, M_{xx} , M_{yy} , M_{xy} , κ_{xx} , κ_{yy} , and κ_{xy} are the out-of-plane moments and curvatures respectively, A_{ij} , B_{ij} , and D_{ij} are the in-plane, coupling, and bending stiffness coefficients respectively, and $()^{(T,H)}$ indicates non-mechanical quantities, i.e. hygral or thermal effects. Since hygrothermal stability can be defined as having the out-of-plane curvatures equal to zero for any change in temperature or moisture, by considering no mechanical resultants, this can be expressed as

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix}^{(T,H)} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

For a laminate where all plies have the same mechanical and hygrothermal properties in their principal material directions, solving Equation (2) produces the necessary and sufficient conditions to ensure hygrothermal stability, given as

$$N_{xx}^{(T,H)} = N_{yy}^{(T,H)} \quad \text{and} \\ N_{xy}^{(T,H)} = M_{xx}^{(T,H)} = M_{yy}^{(T,H)} = M_{xy}^{(T,H)} = 0 \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{or} \\ B_{ij} = 0. \quad (3b)$$

meaning that either (Condition A) the laminate has equal axial in-plane non-mechanical stress resultants and all other resultants are zero or (Condition B) the laminate has a coupling stiffness matrix identically equal to zero. The equations that satisfy these conditions can be cast in terms of the fiber orientation angle, θ_k , and location of each ply within the stacking sequence as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \cos 2\theta_k &= 0 & \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \cos 2\theta_k &= 0 \\ \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \sin 2\theta_k &= 0 & \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \sin 2\theta_k &= 0 \\ \sum_{k=1}^n \cos 2\theta_k &= 0 & \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \cos 4\theta_k &= 0 \\ \sum_{k=1}^n \sin 2\theta_k &= 0 & \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \sin 4\theta_k &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad \text{or} \quad (4a,b)$$

respectively. Since the equations that satisfy either Condition A or Condition B are only functions of k and θ_k , they are material independent. This benefits the designer by allowing for choice of stacking sequence before a material system and provides robustness to the hygrothermal stability from variations in material properties.

4 Optimization Procedure

The stacking-sequence-dependent equations that ensure hygrothermal stability are used as constraints to the optimization procedure. The objective function arises from the compliance coefficients in CLT. To define the objective function, invert Equation (1) to arrive at the mid-plane strains and curvatures as a function of the resultants, given as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_{xx} \\ \kappa_{yy} \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{11} & \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{16} & \beta_{11} & \beta_{12} & \beta_{16} \\ \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{22} & \alpha_{26} & \beta_{12} & \beta_{22} & \beta_{26} \\ \alpha_{16} & \alpha_{26} & \alpha_{66} & \beta_{16} & \beta_{26} & \beta_{66} \\ \beta_{11} & \beta_{12} & \beta_{16} & \delta_{11} & \delta_{12} & \delta_{16} \\ \beta_{12} & \beta_{22} & \beta_{26} & \delta_{12} & \delta_{22} & \delta_{26} \\ \beta_{16} & \beta_{26} & \beta_{66} & \delta_{16} & \delta_{26} & \delta_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx}^{(T,H)} \\ \varepsilon_{yy}^{(T,H)} \\ \gamma_{xy}^{(T,H)} \\ \kappa_{xx}^{(T,H)} \\ \kappa_{yy}^{(T,H)} \\ \kappa_{xy}^{(T,H)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Of interest is the twist rate, φ , and for a hygrothermally stable laminate, the relationship between the twist rate and the extension and bending deformation modes can be found as

$$2\varphi = \kappa_{xy} = \beta_{16} N_{xx} + \delta_{16} M_{xx} \quad (6)$$

Previous work [6,7] has presented optimal hygrothermally stable stacking sequences for extension-twist coupling and bend-twist coupling separately. Specifically, to optimize extension-twist coupling, the objective function is taken to be $-\beta_{16}^2$, because the optimizer minimizes the objective function. The results of the optimization are

provided in Table 1; η is a normalized performance parameter calculated as

$$\eta = |ntE_{xx}\beta_{16}| = \left| \frac{2\phi E_{xx}}{\sigma_{xx}} \right| \approx \left| \frac{2\phi}{\epsilon_{xx}} \right| \quad (7)$$

For bend-twist coupling, the objective function is taken to be $-\delta_{16}^2$. Results from this optimization are provided in Table 2. The normalized performance parameter, ζ , as given in Table 2, is calculated as

$$\zeta = \left| \frac{\delta_{16}(nt)^3 E_{11}}{12} \right| = |\delta_{16} D_{11}| \approx \left| \frac{\delta_{16} M_{xx}}{\kappa_{xx}} \right| = \left| \frac{2\phi}{\kappa_{xx}} \right| \quad (8)$$

In both cases, the equations that satisfy the hygrothermal stability conditions are implemented as constraints. This work aims at achieving higher twist rates by identifying laminates with both extension-twist and bend-twist couplings and performing a similar optimization procedure.

It is of interest to determine if any stacking sequences that are optimal for one type of coupling have the other. Since all of the optimal bend-twist laminates are symmetric, they will not have extension-twist coupling. The even-ply optimal extension-twist laminates have zero bend-twist

coupling, and the odd-ply optimal extension-twist laminates have less than 2% of the optimal value for a laminate with the same number of plies, as given in Table 2.

5 Combined Extension-bend-twist Coupling

Theoretically, a laminate could be optimal for both extension-twist and bend-twist couplings. If this holds, then

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta|_{optimal}} \frac{\zeta}{\zeta|_{optimal}} = \frac{\delta_{16}}{\delta_{16}|_{optimal}} \frac{\beta_{16}}{\beta_{16}|_{optimal}} = 1 \quad (9)$$

However, it has been shown that the optimal extension-twist laminates did not have optimal bend-twist coupling and the optimal bend-twist laminates had no extension-twist coupling. Therefore, it is of interest to investigate how close to the theoretical upper limit of combined extension-bend-twist is achievable. In this case, the objective function is chosen to be

$$g(\{\theta_k, k=1,2,\dots,n\}) = -(\delta_{16}\beta_{16})^2 \quad (10)$$

The same constrained optimization procedure as described previously is used in conjunction with the Condition A hygrothermal stability constraints to

Table 1. Hygrothermally Stable Laminates with Optimal Extension-twist Coupling

Laminate	Stacking Sequence	η (m ⁻¹)	% Increase in Coupling over Winckler
5-ply	[-58.7/11.4/45/78.6/-31.3]	18985	81.0%
6-ply	[21.2/-63.8/-48.7/48.7/63.8/-21.2]	20820	75.5%
7-ply	[14.1 -76.9 -73.9 45 -16.1 -13.2 75.7]	15369	41.0%
8-ply	[-21.5/72.1/57.9/-29.6/29.6/-57.9/-72.1/21.5]	13654	26.3%
9-ply	[25.5/-79/32.5/-62.9/49.9/27.4/57/-10.6/64.9]	13544	23.6%
10-ply	[16.2/-69.0/-65.3/31.8/42.1/-42.1/-31.8/65.3/69.0/-16.2]	13447	24.7%
Winckler	[22.5/-67.5 ₂ /22.5/-22.5/67.5 ₂ /-22.5]	11495	-

Table 2. Hygrothermally Stable Laminates with Optimal Bending-twist Coupling

# of plies	Stacking Sequence	ζ
2	[30.5] ₂	8.77
3	[-31.6/87.8] _s	8.99
4	[32.8/-88.2] _s	9.16
5	[33.3/-88.4/33.3] _s	9.18
6	[33.5/-88.5/33.5] _s	9.16
7	[33.6/-88.5/33.6/-88.5] _s	9.14
8	[-32.8 ₂ /88.2 ₂] _s	9.16
9	[-33.1 ₂ /88.4 ₅ /-33.1 ₂]	9.18
10	[-33.3 ₂ /88.4 ₂ /-33.3] _s	9.18

allow for extension-twist coupling. The results are provided in Table 3 along with the values for η and ζ for the given laminates. Note that the optimized laminates achieve about 40% of the theoretical upper limit.

Of primary interest is the achievement of maximum twist rate in a laminate. Recall that the twist rate for a laminate undergoing only axial and bending loading can be expressed as given in Equation (6). Note that the contributions from loading cannot be factored from the stacking-sequence-dependent terms any longer. But a simplification can be made whereby only a relative loading parameter remains. Dividing both sides of Equation (6) by M_{xx} , the equation for twist rate per unit moment resultant is given as

$$\frac{2\varphi}{M_{xx}} = \frac{\kappa_{xy}}{M_{xx}} = \beta_{16} \frac{N_{xx}}{M_{xx}} + \delta_{16} = \beta_{16}\alpha + \delta_{16} \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the objective function to be minimized is given as

$$g = -(\beta_{16}\alpha + \delta_{16})^2 \quad (12)$$

The value of α will depend on the application and flight regime. Since this work is not associated with a particular application, flat strips of unit width were taken to represent the structure, and various values of α were chosen to demonstrate the effects of varying load conditions. Because of the difference in order of magnitude between β_{16} and δ_{16} when considering flat strips, α was chosen in the range $[2 \cdot 10^3 \text{ m}^{-1}, 2 \cdot 10^4 \text{ m}^{-1}]$ to demonstrate variations in the optimal stacking sequences as the contribution of extension-twist and bend-twist couplings change.

Since optimizations must be performed for each value of α , only the six-ply laminate was chosen for this investigation. Table 4 presents the results of these optimizations, along with the levels of each coupling. Also included are the results when α equals zero and infinity, corresponding to zero axial force and zero bending moment, respectively.

The results in Table 4 demonstrate there is an $\alpha \approx 4000/\text{m}$ below which the optimal bend-twist coupling solution is optimal. Since the optimal bend-twist coupling solution is symmetric, there is no extension-twist coupling. Physically, this means that there is insufficient axial force to justify using a stacking sequence capable of producing extension-twist coupling. For $\alpha > 4000/\text{m}$ the optimal laminates have both extension-twist and bend-twist couplings. As α is increased, the stacking sequence trends toward the optimal extension-twist coupled laminate. Since this laminate is antisymmetric, it is incapable of producing bend-twist coupling, and likewise as $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$, $\zeta \rightarrow 0$. This investigation demonstrates that the optimal laminate will depend on the loading conditions specific to each application.

6 Sensitivity to Errors in Ply Angle

The optimal stacking sequences presented herein would not be useful if small errors in ply angle result in significant loss of coupling. To this end, a study was undertaken to establish the reduction in coupling due to small perturbations in fiber orientation angle. To model manufacturing errors within a given laminate, the fiber orientation angle of each lamina was varied on a uniform interval of $\theta_k \pm 2^\circ$. The six-ply stacking sequence in Table 4 corresponding to $\alpha = 6000/\text{m}$ was chosen for this study. A Monte Carlo simulation was performed wherein a set of 10^5 perturbed stacking sequences was created, and the relative twist curvature was calculated using Equation (11).

Figure 1 presents a histogram of the results from both laminates. The error is mostly contained to within 5% of the expected coupling. It should be noted that the error can be positive even though the stacking sequence yields maximum coupling because layups with perturbed ply angles are not subject to the hygrothermal stability conditions of

Table 3. Hygrothermally Stable Laminates with Optimal Extension-bend-twist Coupling

n	Stacking Sequence	η (m^{-1})	ζ
5	[60.5 / -9.6 / -43.2 / -76.8 / 33.1]	18862	3.85
6	[76.9 / 6.9 / -12.3 / -62.8 / -82.0 / 28.0]	11996	5.56
7	[82.8 / 5.6 / -26.6 / 40.1 / -63.9 / -70.4 / 26.4]	13271	4.61
8	[66.4 / 20.6 / -27.2 / -51.9 / -64.3 / 29.6 / -74.2 / 28.3]	10988	4.92
9	[82.4 / 5.4 / 43.8 / -29.0 / -46.3 / -61.7 / 36.0 / -72.6 / 29.2]	9330	5.02
10	[72.2 / 46.6 / -1.7 / -14.3 / -37.8 / -58.8 / -73.2 / -78.6 / 31.3 / 29.9]	8767	5.31

the optimal laminate, and as such the resulting perturbed laminate may not be strictly hygrothermally stable.

5 Conclusions

Taking advantage of extension-twist coupling and bend-twist coupling has the potential to produce higher levels of twist rate in composite laminates as compared to either type of coupling alone. The twist rate depends on both the loading conditions and blade structure. This work demonstrates that, depending on the loading experienced by a particular blade, there are cases when a design optimized for bend-twist coupling would be preferable, and other cases when a design optimized for combined extension-twist and bend-twist would be preferable.

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Fig. 1. Robustness of Extension-bend-twist Coupled Six-ply Laminate with Optimal Twist Rate

Table 4. Hygrothermally Stable Laminates with Optimal Twist Rate from Combined Extension and Bending

α (m ⁻¹)	Stacking Sequence	η (m ⁻¹)	ζ
0	[33.5/-88.5/33.5] _s	0	9.16
2000	[33.5/-88.5/33.5] _s	0	9.16
4000	[33.5/-88.5/33.5] _s	0	9.16
6000	[77.5 / 7.7 / -12.0 / -61.8 / -81.5 / 28.7]	11710	5.69
8000	[76.1 / 5.6 / -12.7 / -64.2 / -82.6 / 27.0]	12380	5.36
10000	[70.5 / -27.8 / -32.7 / 46.0 / 31.4 / -64.3]	19906	0.87
12000	[70.0 / -28.2 / -33.7 / 45.0 / 31.1 / -64.7]	20071	0.75
14000	[69.5 / -26.1 / -39.5 / 41.9 / 28.6 / -67.1]	20764	0.11
16000	[69.4 / -26.2 / -39.7 / 41.8 / 28.3 / -67.3]	20781	0.10
18000	[69.2 / -26.3 / -39.9 / 41.7 / 28.2 / -67.4]	20791	0.08
20000	[69.2 / -26.4 / -40.0 / 41.6 / 28.0 / -67.5]	20798	0.07
→∞	[-68.8 / 26.2 / 41.3 / -41.3 / -26.2 / 68.8]	20820	0